

New European Bauhaus Academy

NEB Junction: Open NEB platforms for sharing Knowledge

1st New European Bauhaus Academy Conference

Barcelona, February 27, 2026

Aksel Borgen
NTNU

Circular Bio-based Europe
Joint Undertaking

The NEB Hub for Results & Impact

Working Lunch, NEB Junction, photo: Ars Electronica/Martin Hieslmair

[LEARN / GET INSPIRED](#)

Co-designing urban Development Projects in Stavanger, Norway

Participative Approaches Tested in the District of Pedersgata, Pilot Site of the NEB-STAR Project

[CO-DESIGN](#)[CO-BENEFITS](#)[URBAN TRANSFORMATION](#)[NEIGHBOURHOOD REGENERATION](#)

Story

Testing participatory approaches to inform the city's Territorial Transformation Plan

Search ×

I want to ... ▼

About ... ▼

In Region ... ▼

I am... ▼

Tags

Housing

Public Spaces

Vulnerable Communities

Social Innovation

Territorial Transition

Transformation

Impact

TIMBERHAUS

Climate-smart, circular, and sustainable solutions for use of wood in the construction sector

TIMBERHAUS develops solutions for the greater use of timber such as hardwoods and post-consumer wood in the construction sector, with circularity as part of a broader system and design loop. It works collaboratively with partner cities to test solutions and co-create decarbonisation strategies.

by TEKNOLOGISK INSTITUT

2024-2028

Copenhagen // Denmark

Funding Call: HORIZON-CL6-2024-CLIMATE-01-5

Funding Source: ERDF/NEB Prizes

4M - 1M €

→ [EU Reference](#)

→ [Neb Gem](#)

NEB Impact Assessment

Monitoring system
& knowledge
analysis

Decision Support

Recommendations
to decision-makers

Future of NEB

Support
implementation of
NEB Facility + what
comes next

Impact Workshop, NEB Junction, photo: A. Lelo

Town Hall, NEB Junction, photo: vog.photo

Youth Enterprises Workshop, NEB-STAR, photo: Ungt Entreprenørskap

NEB Summer School

NEB Neighbourhoods in
Global Tech Competitiveness

